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Trimetallic BSA-Au-Ag-Fe nanoclusters as a bimodal probe for fluorescence and magnetic resonance imaging.

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ABSTRACT

This article refers about a synthesis of trimetallic nanoclusters (TNCs) consisting of Au, Ag, Fe ions capped by bovine serum albumin (BSA). Manufactured TNCs and their/bimetallic and monometallic siblings were characterised by fluorescence spectroscopy; and the quantum yield (QY). Changes in secondary protein structure, charge, and size of BSA for each type of metal ions were investigated using circular dichroism (CD), zeta-potential, and dynamic light scattering (DLS). This is the first full report analysing the effect of the aforementioned metal ions on BSA *via* microwave assisted synthesis. Finally, the as-prepared TNCs underwent biocompatibility tests by the Alamar Blue assay performed on the Hep G2 carcinoma cell line to determine the limit concentrations of TNCs cell toxicity. We presume as-synthesised TNCs may potentially serve as a fluorescence and MRI bimodal probes due to their good tolerance by the Hep G2 cell line at relatively high metal concentrations.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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1. Introduction

Trimetallic nanoclusters (TNCs) are very attractive materials for many applications. The first works dealing with trimetallic nanoclusters date back to 2003, when their synthesis, characteristic properties, self-assembling core/shell structure, size and applications were introduced [1,2]. Recently, TNCs including

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nanoparticles (NPs), nanodendrites (NDs), nanoclusters (NCs) and modulated bimetallic NCs have been investigated [3–6]. TNCs containing three different metal ions within a composite, can be formed (i) by metal alloying of heterogeneous metals forming NPs, NDs, and NCs [2–5], (ii) using metal ions bound to ligands which are attached to the surface of preformed bimetallic NCs [6–8] (iii) or by laser ablation process as reported by [9].

Frequently, TNCs have been used as efficient catalysts for various chemical reactions that produce complex molecules [10]. They have also served as an essence for the formation of NPs, which were further used as catalysts [11]. Recently, a hybrid composed of NCs and NPs has been used as an efficient electrocatalyst for alkaline water-to-hydrogen/oxygen conversion [12]. Synthesized NPs and NDs can also be used for a p-nitrophenol reduction [4], the removal of aqueous diclofenac [13], as an efficient catalyst for the reductive hydrodehalogenation of aryl and aliphatic halides [3], the hydrogen evolution and oxygen reduction reactions [14], as a probe for simultaneous voltametric detection of ascorbic acid, dopamine, acetaminophen [15]. However, the metallic parts of these NPs and NDs exceed 2 nm, therefore, none of them possess fluorescent properties.

In contrast to the above-mentioned NPs and NDs mentioned above, NCs containing Au atoms assembled into nanostructures smaller than 2 nm in diameter are well known for their fluorescent properties [16,17]. As it has been shown in [5], changes in the dopant/ligand lead to changes in the shape and composition changes of the structure of the alloyed trimetallic NCs. These changes induced a strong enhancement of the quantum yield (QY) [5].

Bimodal or multimodal nanoprobe have been widely investigated for potential applications in diagnostics as bioimaging *in vivo/in vitro* agents and even for theragnostic (i.e. diagnosis and therapy). For instance, Au-Fe NPs have been reported as potential fluorescent as well as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) probes [18,19]. Au-Fe NPs have served as contrast agents for computed tomography (CT) which could be visualised by two-photon photoluminescence (TPPL) and used in photothermal therapy (PTT) for the treatment of cancer cells [20–23].

Further strategy for bimodal nanoprobe preparation was reported by Liang et al. 2013, who chelated Gd^{3+} ions in cyclodecapeptide of a specific composition which simultaneously biomineralized gold NCs. While complexed Gd^{3+} ions were responsible for the MRI contrast, Au NCs were responsible for the fluorescent properties [24]. There are also other approaches to the formation of multimodal nanoprobe discussed in the literature: upconversion nanoparticles quantum dots (QD), Prussia Blue, Gd(III), and Tb(III) were combined with various ligands to achieve required multimodal properties such as MRI, CT contrast, optical visualization, PTT and photodynamic therapy (PDT) [23,25–27].

Another dual emitting probe has been created by binding the third type of metal ions such as Er into ligands of bimetallic AuAgNCs [7]. As-formed NCs can be used as a probe for the detection of sulphide ions [7]. The detection of Cu, Hg ions is based on a specific interaction with the ligands of AuAgNCs which may have a negative influence on the fluorescence properties [6].

The origin and mechanism of the characteristic fluorescence of bovine serum albumin (BSA), BSA-AuNCs have been investigated by several authors [28–34]. It is generally accepted and described in many reviews, such as [35–37] as well as in the recent paper, e.g. [38] that characteristic red fluorescence of AuNCs stems from quantum confinement effect providing the AuNCs size does not exceed the Fermi wavelength of electrons (single-electron transition assumed). As for Au-AgNCs fluorescence, synergism is considered by [39] and fluorescence features become even more complicated since there are several factors in play, such as: electron or energy exchange and correlation effects between metals, spin-orbit coupling, electronic polarizability etc.

Investigations and advances in the synthesis of Au-AgNCs capped with BSA have recently attracted much attention due to promising properties and wide range of applications [40–43] and as a possible probes for detection of gallic acid, folic acid or ethyl parathion [44–46]. Various types of fluorescent BSA-Au-AgNCs synthesis have been reported [6,40–42, 47,48]. For example, Au-AgNCs can be synthesised by either mixing as-prepared AuNCs and AgNCs at room temperature [42], or by rapid one-pot sono-chemical method which produced Au/AgNCs with yellow emission [48]. The possibility of fast microwave synthesis has been reported by [41,47,49]. Furthermore, thermal synthesis has been developed with a difference in precursor addition/mixing and time/temperature of heating [6,7, 40,43, 50–52]. All Au-AgNCs, prepared by the above mentioned synthesis, have good fluorescence properties and can be

used for metal ion detection or imaging. AuNCs doped with Ag show enhanced fluorescence intensity, fluorescence maximum is blue-shifted and structural changes in BSA are observed [53–55].

Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPION) play a special role in visualising of cells or biological systems *in vivo* by ^1H MRI [56,57]. SPIONs in the form of Fe_3O_4 NPs are frequently created from precursors such as Fe(III) and Fe(II) chlorides [58]. Several authors use BSA as a shell for SPIONs and/or other additives for better *in vivo* biocompatibility and cell targeting [59–61]. In addition to Fe_3O_4 NPs, smaller MRI-active NCs formed by using iron(III) chloride, BSA gallic/ellagic acids and targeting agent were used for PTT of carcinoma disease [62,63]. There has been report of using BSA-AuNCs and SPION by [64] or by use of Fe-metal organic framework nanoparticles [65]. However, there have been no reports on possible combination of Au-AgNCs (representing the fluorescent part) and MRI probes generated by BSA and iron ions so far. Therefore, this is the main aim of this work.

In the present work, we investigate the fluorescence and MRI features of trimetallic nanoclusters which are prepared as a combination of Au(III), Ag(I) and Fe(II) ions mixed together in different mutual molar ratios. BSA is used as a matrix for the formation of fluorescent Au-AgNCs and for the simultaneous capture of Fe(II) ions. In the process of preparing of our samples, synthetic procedures of many authors have inspired us. For example, the choice of Au:Ag ratios was influenced by [40,47]. For the purpose of MRI contrast, we were inspired by [18,19] and their exploitation of Fe ions. As-prepared BSA-Au-Ag-FeTNCs were characterised by using of steady-state fluorescence (including QY determination), dynamic light scattering (DLS), zeta potential measurements, circular dichroism (CD) and UV-visible absorption spectroscopy. MRI contrasts and relaxivity values of BSA-Au-Ag-FeTNCs were determined and the prospective samples underwent tests of viability. As a result of our optimized syntheses, we have successfully and reproducibly prepared trimetallic BSA capped NCs that have good fluorescence properties and MRI contrast and appear be low toxic or non-toxic to cells under certain conditions, thus making them potentially promising as multimodal probes.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Chemicals

All chemicals used in our experiments were analytical grade and used without any further purification. $\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\geq 99.9\%$, AgNO_3 , $\geq 99.9999\%$, $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ purist p.a., $\geq 99.0\%$ and NaOH Bio Ultra, for luminescence, $\geq 98.0\%$, BSA $\geq 98.0\%$, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany.

2.2. Synthesis of BSA-protected NCs containing Au-Ag-Fe

For the synthesis of trimetallic BSA-Au-Ag-Fe nanoclusters with a molar of ratio 5:1:1, labelled as BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs, the aqueous solution of $\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 mL, 10 mM) was mixed with the aqueous solution of AgNO_3 (2 mL, 10 mM) at room temperature. After stirring for 90 s at room temperature, this solution was added to water solution of BSA (20 mL, 40 mg/mL) under vigorous stirring and filled with appropriate volume of Milli-Q water so that the final volume of the solution was 44 mL. After stirring for 90 s at room temperature, the solution of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 mL, 10 mM) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for another 90 s. Finally, NaOH solution (2 mL, 1 M) was added to adjust the pH to 11 and the reaction mixture was stirred for 90 s before being placed in a microwave oven (max. power of 700 W), which was set at 20% of power for 40 s. Twenty seconds after the first period, a shorter period of microwave irradiation (20% for 10 s) of the reaction mixture was used. The temperature of the reaction mixture was raised to 55°C and then slowly cooled to room temperature. Due to maturation processes, the prepared samples were kept at room temperature for a period of 150 min. Dialysis against deionised water was then carried out for 1 h in 2 L beaker, followed by replacement of deionised water and a further dialysis period of 19 h of dialysis took place to eliminate the presence of any free metal and additional ions in the final system. Sonication was employed to break up any possible agglomerates of BSA formed before and after dialysis. After dialysis, the system was concentrated using Spin-X UF concentrators (50 kDa MWCO PES membrane, 20 mL, Sigma-Aldrich, Schnellendorf, Germany). Several variants of concentrated solutions of the same sample were prepared: 1x, 2x, 4x, and 5x concentrated. These

correspond to the theoretical concentration of Au ions incorporated in BSA (2.27, 4.54, 9.08, 11.35 mM), respectively. Injection syringe filters (PES membrane pore size 220 nm, 33 mm, Merck, Millex, Tullagreen, Ireland) were used to avoid the formation of random BSA agglomerates in solutions, except for highest 5x concentration due to technical difficulty. The final solutions were stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C to avoid protein degradation.

The BSA-5:2:2 ratio of Au-Ag-Fe labelled as BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs was synthesised very similarly to BSA-5:1:1, i.e. with the same precursor concentrations, however the solutions of AgNO₃ and FeCl₂·6H₂O were added in a double volume during the preparation procedure. The next steps of the synthesis procedure, system maturation, purification, concentrate formation, and storage were the same for both types BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs which can be further labelled as BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs.

The bimodal BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs which can be further labelled as BSA-Au-Ag BSA((a), (b))NCs with molar ratios (5:1:0, 5:2:0) were synthesised in the same way as their TNCs siblings but without using FeCl₂·4H₂O as the Fe precursor. All the other steps of the synthetic procedure, system maturation, purification, concentrate formation, and storage, were the same for both types of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs.

The monomodal variants BSA-Au(5:0:0)NCs, BSA-Ag(0:1:0, 0:2:0)NCs, BSA-Fe (0:0:1, 0:0:2)NCs were synthesised as follows. The precursors HAuCl₄·3H₂O, AgNO₃, FeCl₂·4H₂O in aqueous solution (10 mL, 10 mM), (2, 4 mL, 10 mM), (2, 4 mL, 10 mM), were mixed with BSA solution (20 mL, 40 mg/mL) under vigorous stirring and filled up with Milli-Q water so that the final volume would be 44 mL, each. After stirring for 90 s, NaOH solution (2 mL, 1 M) was added to adjust the pH to 11. The next steps were the same as described above. The monomodal variants were named BSA-AuNCs, BSA-Ag(a)NCs, BSA-Ag(b)NCs which can be further labelled as BSA-Ag((a), (b))NCs, and BSA-Fe(a)NCs, BSA-Fe(b)NCs which can be further labelled as BSA-Fe BSA-Fe((a), (b))NCs, respectively.

BSA-Treated which underwent the same synthetic procedure as tri-, bi-, or monometallic NCs with the sole exception of the absence of metal precursors, served as the main reference in all cases.

2.3. Fluorescence and quantum yield

To estimate QY of NCs or TNCs the fluorescence spectra were measured on the JASCO FP-8500 (Jasco, Tokyo, Japan) using 1 cm quartz cuvettes. Selected excitation wavelengths were 270, 300 and 465 nm [31,33,34], (further explained in section Quantum yield), and corresponding emission spectra were recorded in the range of 480–850 nm. Recorded data step was 1 nm, scan speed 100 nm/min, response time 0.5 s, excitation and emission bandwidth 5 nm, and medium sensitivity of detector light source Xe lamp. The measurement was repeated 3 times and averaged. Spectral corrections based on the calibrated detector, photons count, blank and on second order Rayleigh scattering filters were applied. The concentration of Au ions during the QY measurement was diluted to 0.011 mM of Au for excitation wavelengths of 270 and 300 nm. For the estimation of QY at 465 nm we used 10x less diluted samples compared to the experiments, where excitation wavelengths 270, 300 nm were used. Visualised fluorescence spectra were recorded in the range 290–850 nm, applied excitation wavelength was 270 nm. Protein concentration of samples BSA-Treated and BSA-Nature was halved due to instrument scale range. Other conditions were the same as for the QY assessment. The measurement was repeated 3 times and averaged. For 3D excitation-emission maps, the excitation range was set to 250–500 nm and emission range was set to 250–850 nm. The recorded data step was 2 nm using scan a speed of 5000 nm/min, response time of 10 ms, excitation and emission bandwidth of 5 nm and medium detector sensitivity. Other conditions were the same as for the QY assessment at excitation wavelength 270 nm.

Excitation spectra were measured in the range 250–570 nm the emission wavelengths used were (625 nm BSA-AuNCs), (585 nm BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs) and (580 nm BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs). Recorded data step was 1 nm, the scan speed was 100 nm/min, the response time was 0.5 s, excitation and emission bandwidth were 5 nm, medium sensitivity of detector and light source Xe lamp was applied.

The UV-vis spectrometer Specord 250 Plus (Analytic Jena AG, Jena, Germany) was used for the correct assessment of the QY. The absorbance of the solution at 270, 300 and 465 nm, bandwidth 2 nm,

response time 0.5 s was determined for the sample in quartz cuvette before each fluorescence spectrum measurement. The concentration of the solution was adjusted to obtain an absorbance value of less than 0.2. The fluorescence of the samples using the excitation at 465 nm was measured at a concentration 10 times higher as than that used for the fluorescence excitation at 270 and 300 nm. Nile Blue (NB) was used as a reference for the evaluation of the QY at 270, 300 and 465 nm excitation wavelengths. The NB 500 nm excitation wavelength was used as a standard [66]. The QY can be calculated according to this formula:

$$QY = QY_r * \frac{I}{I_r} * \frac{A}{A_r} * \frac{n^2}{n_r^2} \quad (1)$$

Where I is an integral of the fluorescence intensity, A is an absorbance, n is a refractive index, and r is a subscript that indicating the reference [67]. The measurement was performed at 295 K, repeated 8 times for each wavelength and averaged. Also, the above mentioned a UV-VIS spectrometer was employed to record absorbance spectra in the range 250–850 nm, bandwidth 2 nm and response time 0.5 s.

2.4. Secondary structure of protein

The secondary structure of the protein was also determined using a circular dichroism JASCO J-815 (Jasco, Tokyo, Japan) in a 0.1 cm quartz cell. CD spectra were recorded in the range of 190–400 nm and each spectrum was the average of 6 scans. The secondary structure was calculated using the Beta Structure Selection (BeStSel) algorithm. The algorithm performed a detailed secondary structure analysis providing information on eight secondary structure components [68,69]. The alpha helix content was also calculated using the molecular residue ellipticity (MRE) according to Equations (2) and (3) based on [70].

$$MRE = \frac{\theta}{10 * c * l * n} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha - (Helix) = \frac{-MRE(208) - 4000}{33000 - 4000} \quad (3)$$

where θ is the ellipticity derived from CD in deg·cm²/mol, c is the molar concentration of the protein (in our case 3 μM), l is the length path of the cell (in our case 0.1 cm), n is the number of amino acid residues (in our case 583), and MRE is determined from the CD spectrum at the wavelength of 208 nm.

2.5. Size and charge of NCs

The hydrodynamic diameter of TNCs or NCs were investigated using the dynamic light scattering instrument Zetasizer Nano ZEN 3600 ZS (Malvern Instrument Ltd, Malvern, UK), equipped with a He-Ne laser (633 nm), at 25 ± 1 °C. The same concentration of samples was used for hydrodynamic diameter measurements as for the fluorescent measurements. The measurement was repeated 6 times and averaged.

The TEM images were acquired by the JEM-1400 Flash electron microscope (JEOL Ltd, Tokyo, Japan) in cooperation with Health institute based in Ostrava. The Cu grids (300 mesh) covered with carbon foil were soaked into the sample droplet casted on the parafilm, then the grid was quickly washed in the droplet of deionized water and the excessive liquid from the grid was removed with the help of filter paper. After that Cu grids were dried spontaneously. For the scanning electron microscopy in bright field (STEM-BF) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis the JEM-2200FS (JEOL Ltd, Tokyo, Japan) was used in cooperation with Department of Physics of Materials, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University. The samples were mixed together with methanol in ration 1:2 after 1 min dropped on the Cu grids (300 mesh) covered with lacey carbon foil laid on filtration paper.

The zeta potential values were recorded on the same instrument. Sample concentrations were diluted to approximately 10 mg/ml of BSA for all samples. The measurement was repeated 10 times and averaged.

Table 1. The relaxivities r_1 and r_2 and iron content for samples with different concentrations.

	Sample	Concentration gradient			
		1x	2x	4x	5x
r_1 [L/mmol.s]	BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
	BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)	0.1	0.6	0.2	0.2
r_2 [L/mmol.s]	BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)	2.4	2.6	2.8	3.1
	BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)	1.5	6.2	2.2	2.4
Fe [mM]	BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)	0.2	0.5	1.1	1.9
	BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)	0.6	0.5	2.1	4.0

Table 2. Parameters of rapid acquisition with relaxation enhancement multi-spin echo MR of T_1 and T_2 weighted sequences.

	Effective echo time [ms]	Time of repetition [ms]	Turbo factor	Scan time [min]	Plane resolution [μm^2]	Slice thickness [mm]
T_1 -weighted sequence	11.6	587	1	10.5	234×195	0.6
T_2 -weighted sequence	36.0	3300	8	11.0	234×195	0.6

2.6. $1H$ magnetic resonance imaging and relaxometry

The MR relaxometry was used to determine the relaxivities $r_{1,2}$ of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe nanoclusters. The relaxation times T_1 and T_2 were measured on a Bruker Minispec mq 60 relaxometer (Bruker Biospin, Ettlingen Germany) at 1.5 T, at stabilized temperature of 37 °C during the whole experiment. Concentration series of 1x, 2x, 4x, and 5x concentrated samples of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs containing theoretical amounts of Fe ions for (a) (0.45, 0.91, 1.82, 2.27 mM) and for (b) (0.9, 1.82, 3.63, 4.54 mM) variant, respectively. These samples were further measured for each concentration in declining concentration gradient as a MR substance 100, 50, 25, 10 and 5% of contrast agent in distilled water. MR sequence for T_1 measurement: Inversion Recovery, 20 points for fitting, 1 excitation, Time of Repetition was 0.01–10000 ms, recycle delay 2s. T_2 relaxation times were measured with Carr-Purcell-Meiboom-Gill method, Time of Repetition was 5000 ms, 20000 echoes, 1 excitation, effective echo time was 0.05 ms, recycle delay 2s. The relaxivities $r_{1,2}$ were calculated via the least-squares curve fitting of R_1 , R_2 relaxation rates s^{-1} versus iron concentration in mM. The experimentally determined solvent relaxation rate R was subtracted from the nanoparticle relaxation rates as a starting value prior to the linear regression analysis.

The magnetic resonance imaging experiments were performed on Bruker Biospec 47/20 (Bruker, Ettlingen, Germany) at 4.7 T. T_1 and T_2 weighted images of each system were acquired using concentration series (100, 50, 25, 10 and 5%) of the iron content, see Table 1. Rapid acquisition with relaxation enhancement multi-spin echo MR of T_1 and T_2 weighted sequences were used, and their parameters are listed in Table 2.

MR image processing and quantification were performed using ImageJ software. The contrast to noise ratio (CNR) was calculated from images as $0.655 \times |\text{Sig}_{\text{sample}} - \text{Sig}_{\text{water}}| / \sigma_{\text{noise}}$ where Sig is signal intensity in the region of interest, σ is the standard deviation of background noise and constant 0.655 reflects the Rician distribution of background noise in a magnitude MR image. The fractional signal loss (FSL) was calculated as a percentage of the signal drop/loss in phantoms related to the water signal intensity.

2.7. Cell viability test

The Alamar blue assay (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) was used to estimate the viability of cells treated with TNCs or BSA-Treated. For cell viability, the human hepatoma cell line HepG2 was seeded in a 96-well plate (20 000 cells per well) and incubated for 24 h in DMEM low glucose, GlutaMAX (GIBCO, Life Technologies, Grand Island, NY, USA), 10% FBS (VWR, Radnor, PA, USA), Primocin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) (InVivogen, San Diego, CA, USA).

The cells were incubated with BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs containing the highest theoretical concentrations of Au ions 11.35 mM. Cell cultures were treated for 24 h in ratios medium to TNCs 3:1, 2:2, 1:3 with theoretical concentrations of Au ions 2.84, 5.68, 8.51 mM, respectively. As a control, cells grown in plain cell growth medium as well as cell growth medium containing BSA-Treated (1.35 mM) were used. Prior to spectrophotometric analysis, a 10% of Alamar blue solution in cultivation medium was added to

each well and incubated at 37 °C for 4 h. The absorbance was measured at wavelengths of 570 nm and 600 nm using a Tecan Infinite 200 PRO reader (Tecan Group Ltd., Männedorf, Switzerland). The viability of the control was set at 100%. The experiment was performed in triplicates and repeated three times. The formula to count the viability is as follows:

$$\text{Viability}[\%] = \frac{\text{Cell viability in medium with BSA capped NCs}}{\text{Viability of cells in medium}} * 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Viability}[\%] = \frac{\text{Cell viability in medium with BSA capped NCs}}{\text{Viability of cells in medium with BSA – Treated}} * 100 \quad (5)$$

3. Results and discussion

The synthesis procedure went through a lot of optimisation processes, such as: changes the ion ratios to optimise the fluorescence intensity and stability of the samples; finding the optimal content of Fe ions incorporated in BSA to ensure MRI contrast; playing with the final volume of the reaction mixture in conjunction with MW irradiation periods to achieve the desired temperature within the reaction mixture; etc. The properties of the optimised TNCs BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a) and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b) are compared with those of the bimetallic NCs, BSA-Au-Ag(a) and BSA-Au-Ag(b), and the monometallic BSA-Au, BSA-Ag((a), (b)), BSA-Fe((a), (b)), where ((a), (b)) refers to lower or higher molar ratios of Ag and/or Fe ions used in the synthesis process. Sample BSA-Treated was used as a main reference. It should be noted that several properties such as fluorescence spectra, zeta-potential, protein structure of our BSA-Treated were also compared with those of BSA-Nature, as many researchers are using BSA-Nature as their main reference.

3.1. Optical properties of synthesised NCs

In order to evaluate and compare the fluorescence properties of our samples, fluorescence spectra were measured using three excitation wavelengths of 270, 300 and 465 nm, and corresponding emission spectra were recorded in the range of 480–850 nm. Furthermore, 3D excitation-emission maps were measured for fluorescent nanoclusters with an excitation range set at 250–500 nm and an emission range set at 250–850 nm. Furthermore, QY of fluorescent nanoclusters was estimated using Nile blue as a standard.

3.1.1. Fluorescence properties of nanoclusters

To compare the fluorescence properties of BSA-Nature, BSA-Treated and BSA-AuNCs formed in the presence of silver and iron, we measured the fluorescence spectra shown in Figure 1(a). Obviously, there are differences in the fluorescence features of the BSA-Nature and BSA-Treated: (I) The fluorescence intensity of BSA-Nature is about 10% higher than that of BSA-Treated in the UV region. (II) There is a blue-shift of the fluorescence emission maximum in the UV region – from 335 nm (BSA-Nature) to 325 nm (BSA-Treated). The spectral shift may be caused by changes in the protein structure during the treatment process as well as due to the oxidation of Tyrosine (Tyr) residues (which are one source of the natural fluorescence features of BSA in the UV region; the other source of UV-emission of BSA are Tryptophan (Trp) residues). This spectral shift can be observed in all treated samples BSA-Ag(b), BSA-Au, BSA-Au-Ag(a) and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a). Nevertheless, the position of the BSA UV-peak was not affected by the introduction of Ag and/or Fe ions into the BSA-AuNCs systems. This may indicate that Tyr and Trp residues are not critically affected by the introduction of these ions.

Similar blue-shift of about 10 nm was observed by [34] when comparing BSA-Nature (emission maximum at 345 nm) this band belong to Trp-134 located near the surface of BSA [71] and BSA-AuNCs (335 nm this peak should represent Trp-212 [71,72]). This shows that the tryptophan in the BSA-AuNCs is better shielded and is present in a more hydrophobic environment compared to BSA-Nature[72]. The 10 nm spectral shift is probably caused by the quenching of Trp-134 [71]. However, it should be noted that different excitation wavelengths (280 nm in Raut et al. while 270 nm here), different BSA purity (not

Figure 1. (a) Fluorescence emission spectra of BSA-AuNCs (black), BSA-Ag(b)NCs (red), BSA-Nature (blue), and BSA-Treated (magenta), BSA-Au-Ag(a) (olive) and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a) (pale red) upon the excitation of 270 nm. (b–d) 3D excitation-emission maps of BSA-AuNCs, BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs, respectively.

specified in Raut et al. while 98% here), and the type of synthesis and applied spectral corrections are most likely responsible for the differences in emission maxima when compared.

Importantly, the lowest fluorescence emission intensity within the UV region was observed for fluorescent BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs and BSA-AuNCs compared to BSA-Nature, BSA-Treated and BSA-Ag(b)NCs [Figure 1\(a\)](#). The fluorescence emission peak was observed in the visible region (maximum at 647 nm) for BSA-AuNCs, (see [Figure 1\(a\)](#)), providing the evidence of the formation of characteristic red-fluorescent gold-NCs. This is in agreement with the literature [[16,28, 34,73–76](#)]. Considering BSA-Ag(b)NCs, no such emission peak was observed in the visible region [Figure 1\(a\)](#), which confirms the observation of [[43](#)].

Furthermore, the mixture of gold (III) and silver (I) ions which are added to the BSA solution has induced the characteristic emission peak shift to 615 nm for the sample BSA-Au-Ag(a) illustrated in [Figure 1\(a\)](#). This specific ratio (5:1) of Au:Ag ions added to the BSA solution was intentionally chosen based on the results of [[40](#)], where various ratios of Au/Ag were added into BSA solution and a variable blue shift of the fluorescence maximum depending on the amount of Ag added into the solution was observed. Zhou et al. [[50](#)] also reported that certain ratios of Au:Ag, particularly (7:1 and 4:1),

incorporated into BSA resulted in increased fluorescence intensity compared to BSA-AuNCs [50]. Such findings have been reported by many authors [53–55], but without further blue-shift at the peak position depending on the amount of Ag added. The difference in the observation may be caused due to different type of synthesis which was used by [40,51]. Our study has shown that fluorescence peak of BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs is broader and more intense compared to BSA-AuNCs. This is in agreement with the observations made by [6,40,48]. The further addition of iron(II) ions has neither affected the characteristic fluorescence peak position nor the width of the fluorescence peak of already formed BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs, and only slightly decreased the fluorescence intensity in both UV and visible regions in case of sample BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs. Nevertheless, the position of the BSA UV-peak was not affected by introduction of Ag and/or Fe ions into BSA-AuNCs systems. This may indicate that Tyr and Trp residues are not critically affected by the introduction of these ions.

Moreover, 3D excitation-emission maps were measured from the UV to the near IR region of samples BSA-AuNCs, BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs to obtain information about the excitation wavelengths that can effectively excite these NCs, as shown in Figure 1(b–d), respectively. Obviously, the emission peak of BSA-AuNCs is relatively broad, asymmetric and the excitation wavelengths ranging from 250 to 500 nm can be applied to obtain the characteristic red-fluorescence emission. Compared to bimetallic BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs (Figure 1(c)) and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs (Figure 1(d)), where the emission peak is broader, originating from yellow to red emission, also asymmetric and with slightly better excitation potential in the violet-blue region compared to BSA-AuNCs (Figure 1(b)). The decrease in fluorescence intensity due to the longer excitation wavelength may be explained as if the different wavelength may excite different structure in the protein. For example, the excitation wavelength 270 nm can excite Trp, Tyr, and NCs in the protein and as expected, the fluorescence intensity is highest for this excitation wavelength. The excitation wavelength 300 nm can excite only Trp and NCs and the wavelength 465 nm is likely to excite NCs. Thus, it can lead to suspicion that some kind of energy transfer between domains (amino acid residues) of the BSA and NCs may occur, as stated by several authors [30,31, 33,34]. Another aspect is that by prolonging the excitation wavelength, the absorption as well as the energy provided to the system of NCs decreases. Therefore, we further examined these excitation wavelengths and used them to calculate QY see Table S1 in Supporting information or Figure 3 [48,51, 75–77].

In Addition, we investigated the influence of higher iron (II) content on the fluorescence properties of the BSA-Au-AgNCs mixture. To achieve a higher molar ratio of Fe ions, we also elevated the concentration of Ag ions to ensure the electrochemical stability of the samples without agglomeration/precipitation. The samples BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs with increased Ag and Fe concentration were measured, respectively. As described in Figure 2(a) the addition of Ag ions at a higher ratio resulted in a blue-shifted fluorescence emission peak with a maximum around 595 nm compared to samples with a lower molar ratio of Ag ions. A similar peak position of the emission maximum for the observed Au:Ag ratio was reported by [40]. However, the fluorescence emission is lower in the UV region, and an even more pronounced decrease was observed in the visible region compared to samples with a lower Ag ratio. The decrease in the fluorescence intensity can be well detected in the 3D excitation-emission maps of samples BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)NCs illustrated in Figure 2(a,b), respectively, compared to their (a) variants shown in Figure 1(c,d). Nevertheless, the mutual comparison of the fluorescence intensity of BSA-Au-Ag(b) and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b) samples revealed that the fluorescence emission of these samples is almost identical and there is almost no negative effect of iron on the fluorescence intensity.

3.1.2. Quantum yield

Fluorescence QY was determined according to Equation (1) to compare the luminescent properties of prepared samples BSA-AuNCs, BSA-Au-AgNCs, BSA-Au-Ag-FeTNCs with respect to Nile Blue dissolved in ethanol. Three excitation wavelengths 270, 300 and 465 nm were chosen depending on the shape of the 3D spectrum of BSA-AuNCs Figure 1(a). The reason for using these wavelengths was that each excitation wavelength could excite a diverse part of the protein structure. The excitation wavelength of 270 nm can excite Trp, Tyr and NCs, prolonged excitation wavelength 300 nm is able to excite only Trp and NCs and visible wavelength 465 nm excites probably solely NCs [31,33,34].

Figure 2. (a) Fluorescence emission spectra of BSA-AuNCs (black), BSA-treated (magenta), BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs (olive), BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs (pale red), Au-Ag(b)NCs (green) and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs (pale grey) upon the excitation of 270 nm. (b,c), 3D excitation-emission maps of BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs, respectively.

The quantum yields and deviations determined for the samples discussed above are listed in SI Table S1 and Figure 3. The highest QY of 8.2% was obtained for BSA-AuNCs when excited at 465 nm. This finding is in agreement with [75]. Rather lower QY of about 6% was determined by [29]. Much lower QY 2% was measured by [51]. These authors used the visible excitation wavelength. The quantum yield determined by excitation wavelengths at 270 and 300 nm is 2.3% and 3%, respectively, and was significantly lower than in the visible region, but comparable to the authors [78–80]. However, Liu et al. determined QY of their samples is 8% with respect to rhodamine B and excitation 365 nm [48]. Andryšková et al. reported a high 6.2% QY of BSA-AuNCs using excitation wavelength 280 nm [76]. Detailed information on synthesis and properties of selected BSA-AuNCs including size, excitation and emission wavelength, QY, QY's standard as described in the literature can be found in Table 3.

Quantum yield of the samples BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)NCs determined using excitation wavelengths 270 and 300 nm are very comparable. The calculated values were approximately 2.7% and 3.5%, respectively. This finding is comparable to Turcsányi et al. who estimated the QY of Au:Ag ratios about 9:1 capped by BSA to be approximately 2.5% using an excitation wavelength of 365 nm [80].

Figure 3. Determined QY of samples BSA-AuNCs, BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs, BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs. Used excitation wavelengths 270 nm empty square, 300 nm empty triangle and 465 nm full round. Data are expressed as a mean of three experiments \pm standard error of the mean.

These authors reported a higher QY [6,47,48]. Zhang et al. determined QY of their GSH capped sample in ratio of Au:Ag 5:1 to be 7.8% when excitation wavelength 380 nm was applied [47]. Liu et al. estimated the QY of their bimetallic BSA-Au-AgNCs in the Au:Ag ratio of 9:1 to be 9.6%, respectively, to excitation of 365 nm [48]. Zhang et al. used Au:Ag ratio of 4.2:1 for the synthesis of their BSA capped NCs and determined that QY was 10.5% with respect to excitation wavelength 370 nm [6]. When the excitation wavelength in the visible region was applied, Sun et al. determined QY of the BSA-Au-AgNCs to be 3.4% using an Au:Ag ratio of 10:2 [52] and Jiang et al. to be 4% [51], which is lower when compared to BSA-Au-Ag((a), (b))NCs 6.8% and 5.2%, respectively. In Table 3, detailed information on the synthesis of selected BSA-Au-AgNCs is given, in conjunction with the size, excitation and emission wavelength, QY, QY's standard of QY as described in the literature maximum (maxima) of their fluorescence emissions of BSA-Au-AgNCs.

However, the QY determined by use of excitation wavelength of 465 nm was no longer comparable for the BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs samples. While the determined QY of BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs (6.8%) was still relatively comparable to BSA-AuNCs (8.2%). The quantum yield of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs drops to only 3.8%. At the same time, it should be noted that the QY of BSA-AuNCs measured in the UV region (270 and 300 nm) was lower than that of BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs.

Described results indicate that the samples with the higher molar ratio of silver and/or iron ions samples BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs have a lower QY than the samples with a lower molar ratio of these ions, i.e. BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs and BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs samples, respectively. This is valid for all three excitation wavelengths (270, 300 and 465 nm) used, see Figure 3 or SI Table S1. This is in an agreement with the results of Zhang et al. who estimated the QY of Ag:Au ratios 0.2, 0.5 to be 7.8% and 4.3%, respectively [47].

Thus, these results indicate that gold ions play a crucial role in the process of forming fluorescent NCs as the highest QY was observed only in the mixture of BSA-AuNCs. Consequently, silver ions might have an enhancing effect on the fluorescence intensity and QY of gold NCs depending on the excitation wavelength applied and probably change the conformation of the protein and the structural size of gold NCs. The value of QY is strongly dependent on the absorbance of the sample at a specific wavelength. As can be observed, absorbance spectra of mono, bimetallic and TNCs namely BSA-AuNCs, BSA-Au-AgNCs and BSA-Au-Ag-FeTNCs differ, see SI Figure S1(A-C). A similar trend can be observed for the excitation spectra of mono, bi NCs and TNCs, see SI Figure S1(D), but without negative effect of Fe ions. The excitation spectra show that BSA-AuNCs can be excited by longer excitation wavelengths comparable to BSA-Au-AgNCs or TNCs. This could be explained by the theory that Ag ions somehow influence the size of the gold clusters embedded inside the BSA. We speculate that the probably the best excitation range for BSA-Au-AgNCs in our case would be 390–440 nm. We have observed moderate enhancing

effect of silver ions of sample BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs on QY when excitation wavelengths of 270 and 300 nm were used. However, the sample BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs shows decrease in the QY compared to BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs and BSA-AuNCs. This finding is partly consistent with the results of Zhang et al. [47] who observed that certain ratios of Au:Ag ions (5:1) have a beneficial effect on QY compared to another ratio of 2:1 ions embedded in GSH [47]. We can speculate that there is no linear trend in the effect of added Ag concentration on QY enhancement. In addition, the tuneable role of Ag ions on the fluorescence peak position seems to be non-linear and dependent on the type of synthesis employed by the authors [40,51–53].

When we compare the QYs and fluorescence intensity of BSA-Au, BSA-Au-Ag(a) or BSA-Au-Ag(b) it is apparent that the fluorescence intensity is high when the excitation wavelength in UV region is applied, however the QYs are relatively low, and vice versa, the QYs are high and the fluorescence intensity low when the excitation wavelength in the visible region is used. This is due to factors, one of them being absorbance which plays a crucial role in Equation (1) for the calculating of QYs and the fact that we are not able to separate or dissect only the absorbance of NCs solely. Thus, in the process of calculating QYs in the UV region large part of the absorbance value is contributed by the protein BSA, nevertheless in visible region the contribution of BSA to the absorbance value is low or even negligible see Figure S1. Other factors that play a role are the excitation wavelength (we cannot completely exclude that some NCs may not be excited by certain wavelengths) and possibility of energy transfer between the BSA and NCs in UV excitation which has already been pointed out by the authors [30,31, 33,34].

On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the trend of QY in samples with and without Fe(III), while the QY of samples without iron BSA-Au-Ag((a), (b))NCs increases when using longer excitation wavelengths; in the samples with iron BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs, the increase of QY is much less pronounced when using excitation in the visible region see Figure 3. In conclusion, iron seems to have a rather negative effect on the QY obtained by excitation wavelength at 465 nm. This is due to the higher absorption caused by added Fe ions; see SI Figure S1(A).

3.2. Size and charge of NCs

DLS has been used successfully for determination of the size of BSA-AuNCs by [76]. In comparison to frequently used transmission electron microscopy (TEM), high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM), DLS measurements are performed directly in aqueous solutions, without the need to dry the samples, and often in dilutions that are also typically used for fluorescence measurements. Moreover, there is a minimal risk of sample transformation during DLS measurements (using a low-energy laser beam of 633 nm) compared to the exploitation of high-energy electrons, which are reduction species and may cause burns or twisting of mesh foils. The size or hydrodynamic diameter of the NCs envelope is one of the crucial aspects that affect the possibility of biological application in cells [49,81–83]. However, many authors employed HR-TEM/TEM instrument that revealed the size of the metallic core of NCs but not its envelope [41,43, 48–50]. However, the size determination using variants of TEM is somewhat inconsistent; see Tables 3 and 4. Nevertheless, we acquired TEM images that shows whole scaffold of chained BSA that are being contrasted due to incorporation of metal ions of trimetallic BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs. As you can see in Figure 4(a,b) the scaffold may be of various shape and length of chain. In some parts there are some darker spots/dots that are probably agglomerates of NCs or maybe small NPs. However, when the higher magnification is applied it looks like the agglomerates may consists of units to tens of NCs smaller than 2 nm Figure 4(c). This observation is in consistent with some other authors, see Tables 3 and 4. No such chained scaffold was observed for the BSA-AuNCs or BSA-Au-AgNCs(b) as you can see in Figure 5. This probably may be due to lower negative charge in case of BSA-AuNCs and BSA-Au-AgNCs(b) that does not repel other clusters from each other and does not attract them to bond only to certain parts with opposite charge to form such scaffold as could be seen for the BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs in Figure 4(a,b). However, it must be noted that the shape and size of the visualised structure of BSA scaffold may also be affected by the process of preparation of the samples for the measurement under the TEM.

Furthermore, we were able to obtain STEM and EDS elemental mapping of samples BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs, BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs and BSA-AuNCs, see Figures 5, Figure S8, Figure S6, respectively. As can be

Table 3. Details of selected BSA-AuNCs preparations and properties as reported in literature.

Authors	Size of BSA-AuNCs [nm]	Excitation wavelength [nm]	Emission wavelength maxima [nm]	Quantum yield [%]	Quantum yield standard	Synthesis condition (X = BSA + HAuCl ₄)
Xie et al. 2009	0.8 TEM	470	640	≈6	Fluorescein	X (2 min)+NaOH → incubation at 37 °C for 12 h
Liu et al. 2011	1.8 HR-TEM	365	670	8	Rhodamine B	X (2min) → NaOH→ ultrasonic irradiation pH 12
Zhang et al. 2014	2 DLS	370	635	6	Quinine Sulfate	X (5min) → NaOH→ 37 °C 12h.
Zhang et al. 2015	n.a.	380	610	2.2	Quinine Sulfate	GSH+ HAuCl ₄ min → MW 90 °C 3 min incubation at RT 3 h. pH 7.4
Hsu & Lin 2016	2.1 ± 0.3 TEM	350	650	1.9	Quinine Sulfate	X → NaOH → MW (120 W, 2 min)
Govindaraju et al. 2017	4–6 TEM	450	650	≈8	Instrument Fluoro-Q2100	X (30 min) + NaOH→ incubation at 50 °C for 3–4 h.
Chuang & Lin 2017	4.2 ± 0.5 TEM	375	677	4.14	Riboflavin-5'-phosphate	X → NaOH → MW (incubation at 80 °C for 4 min)
Jiang et al. 2018	9.5 DLS	400	620	2	Instrument FLSP920	X (5min) → NaOH→ 37 °C 24h.
Andrýšková et al. 2020	3.6 DLS	280	650	6.2	Tryptophan	X (90 s) + NaOH → MW (150 W, 10 s) (pH = 11)
Turcsányi et al. 2023	700–750 DLS	360	660	1.47	JASCO ILF-835 Integration sphere	X(time)→NaOH→25–25 °C 16h.

Table 4. Details of selected BSA-Au-AgNCs preparations and properties as reported in literature.

Authors	Size of BSA-Au-AgNCs [nm]	Excitation wavelength [nm]	Emission wavelength maxima [nm]	Quantum yield [%]	Quantum yield standard	Synthesis condition (X = BSA + HAuCl ₄ + AgNO ₃)
Liu et al. 2011	2.4 HR-TEM	365	620	9.6	Rhodamine B	X (2min) → NaOH→ ultrasonic irradiation
Zhang et al. 2014	4.5 DLS	370	620	10.5	Quinine Sulfate	X (5min) → NaOH→ 37 °C 12h.
Zhang et al. 2015	≈3.1 DLS	380	618 614	7.8 4.3	Quinine Sulfate	GSH+ HAuCl ₄ + AgNO ₃ 5 min → MW 90 °C 3 min incubation at RT 3 h. pH 7.4
Jiang et al. 2018	10.8 DLS	400	585	4	Instrument FLSP920	X (5min) → NaOH→ 37 °C 24h.
Sun et al. 2019	HR-TEM ≈2	480	570	3.4	Rhodamine 6G	X (90 s) + NaOH → MW (150 W, 10 s) (pH = 11)
Turcsányi et al. 2023	700–750 DLS	365	620	2.47	JASCO ILF-835 Integration sphere	X(time)→NaOH→25–25 °C 16h.

seen the placement of metallic ions, such as Au, Ag, Fe are mainly detected in locations with higher contrast, non-metallic ions, e.g. O, S, C, N are also detected in locations with high contrast and around it. However, our images do not allow us to pinpoint the exact location of bonding the metallic ions to non-metallic, thus we can only speculate which metallic ions bind to which non-metall. Additionally, EDS spectra of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs and BSA-AuNCs can be found in [Figure 6](#) and [Figure S7](#), respectively. It has to be noted that in the spectrums are peaks of Cu originated from Cu grids.

Two types of distributions obtained by DLS measurement are shown: based on intensity changes and based on the number of particles in solution are listed in [Table 5](#). Our findings on the size of BSA-Treated and BSA-AuNCs ([Table 5](#)) are in agreement with the values revealed by Andrýšková et al. where the average size of BSA after acidification and alikalisiation reached 10 ± 1.7 nm; while that of BSA-AuNCs was 13.6 ± 3.5 nm, respectively [76]. Thus, the incorporation of Au ions leads to the increase in hydrodynamic diameter of approximately 4 nm in [76], while in the present study is about 5 nm when comparing BSA-Treated 14 nm and BSA-AuNCs 9 nm. Obviously, this value represents an average and includes many NCs that are attached to multiple binding sites on BSA. Jiang et al. and Zhang et al. also reported similar sizes of BSA-AuNCs 9.5 and 8.2 nm, respectively, obtained by DLS technique [51,81]. The core size distribution of BSA-AuNCs measured by TEM instrument is reported to be heterogeneous, ranging from the smallest size 0.8 nm reported by Xie et al. to the largest size of 4–6 nm reported by Govindaraju et al. [29,75, 78,79]. In addition, the first intensity peak of average size around approximately (9 nm 87%, 14 nm 85%) and the second intensity peak of average sizes (393 nm 13% and 798 nm 14%) we obtained

Figure 4. TEM images of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b), (a) acquired with JEM-1400 magnification $5 \times 10^4 \times$, (b,c) acquired with JEM-2200FS magnification $1 \times 10^6 \times$ and $1 \times 10^7 \times$, respectively.

for BSA-Treated and BSA-AuNCs, respectively, which points to the formation of large aggregates or agglomerates of BSA, relatively similar to those observed by [80]. The process of forming of BSA aggregates due to the change in temperature or medium, for example, in deionised water, has been observed by [84]. When the intensity peaks were recalculated to the number of particles inside in the solution, the particle sizes were 5 and 3 nm for BSA-Treated and BSA-AuNCs, respectively.

When we compare BSA-AuNCs and BSA-Ag((a), (b))NCs one can observe a comparable size of the most pronounced peak 85% around 14 nm. We have detected medium sized particles around 110 nm 17% only in BSA-Ag(b) followed by formation of very large BSA aggregates with proximity size around 2100 nm 10%, 3700 3% for BSA-Ag((a), (b))NCs, respectively. Size of BSA-AgNCs is larger compared to BSA-AuNCs according to the number of particles.

In addition, we can compare BSA-AuNCs and BSA-Fe((a), (b))NCs. The particle size of the first intensity peak 27% and 18% is 8 nm for, followed by the most pronounced peak with intensities of 73% and 82% with sizes of 163 and 116 nm for the ratios ((a), (b)), respectively [61]. The sizes of BSA-FeNCs are slightly larger around 5 nm compared to BSA-AuNCs according to number of particles [59,60]. It appears

Figure 5. TEM images of BSA-AuNCs (a) and BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs (b), acquired with JEM-2200FS magnification $2 \times 10^6 \times$, respectively.

Figure 6. STEM and EDS analysis of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs sample: (a) STEM image, scale bar of 20 nm; (b–f) spatial distribution of elements O, S, Ag, Au, Fe, respectively, scale bar 20 nm.

that abundant medium size particles are formed in samples BSA-FeNCs according to intensities related to the particle size.

DLS measurement of bimetallic BSA-Au-Ag((a), (b))NCs (Table 5) revealed a trimodal particle size distribution in both ratios. The most pronounced peak 47% at size 7 nm in the and 54% at size 10 nm for BSA-Au-Ag((a), (b))NCs, respectively. Followed by the second peak (4% in (a) and 41% in (b)) with size an average size around 50 nm. While the first one is consistent with the values for BSA-Au; the second may indicate the formation of BSA dimers or trimers. The least third peak (5% in both cases) with an average size around 3450 nm could be attributed to either the formation of huge BSA aggregates, even though the samples were filtrated prior to measurements. In comparison to BSA-AuNCs, the introduction of silver led to the formation of medium sized particles (average size around 50 nm), as well as huge aggregates/agglomerates in BSA-Au-AgNCs (average sizes exceeding 3 microns). The particle size distribution

Figure 7. The EDS spectrum of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs.

Table 5. Particle size distributions of BSA-Treated, BSA-AuNCs, BSA-Fe((a), (b))NCs, BSA-Ag((a), (b))NCs, BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)NCs determined by DLS. Intensity peaks listed by size distribution from smallest to largest of the sample, size deviation and percentage distribution. Column number of particles represents recalculation to the number of particles by size distribution inside cuvette.

Sample	Intensity peak 1			Intensity peak 2			Intensity peak 3			Number of particle		
	SIZE [nm]	DEV. [nm]	%	SIZE [nm]	DEV. [nm]	%	SIZE [nm]	DEV. [nm]	%	SIZE [nm]	DEV. [nm]	%
BSA-Treated	9	1	87	393	432	13	–	–	–	5	1	100
BSA-Au	14	4	85	798	507	14	–	–	–	3	1	100
BSA-Fe(a)	8	1	27	163	17	73	–	–	–	5	1	100
BSA-Fe(b)	8	1	18	116	8	82	–	–	–	5	1	100
BSA-Ag(a)	16	2	90	–	–	–	2088	721	10	6	1	100
BSA-Ag(b)	11	2	80	111	51	17	3734	542	3	5	1	100
BSA-Au-Ag(a)	7	4	47	45	26	45	3442	969	5	4	1	100
BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)	7	1	21	34	7	28	259	31	51	4	1	100
BSA-Au-Ag(b)	10	1	54	54	12	41	3485	1120	5	4	1	100
BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)	7	1	16	26	7	18	176	11	66	4	1	100

of the sample according to the number of particles inside in the solution was approximately around 4 nm and was the same for both ratios. The metallic core of bimodal BSA-Au-AgNCs was determined of to be 1.2–6 nm depending on the type of synthesis [41,43, 49,50].

Similarly to the bimetallic BSA-Au-AgNCs, a trimodal particle size distribution was observed in BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs. However, with respect to the relative percentage of each peak (based on measurements of intensity changes as a function of time), significant changes were observed with the introduction of the third metal ion (Fe). The most pronounced peak (51% in (a) and 66% in (b)) now has an average size of around 218 nm, followed by the second peak (28% in (a) and 18% in (b)) with an average size of around 30 nm. The less pronounced peak (21% in case of (a) and 16% in case (b)) has an average size of 7 nm. Compared to bimetallic BSA-Au-AgNCs, the introduction of iron led to the formation of large particles with an average size around of 218 nm, which has played a dominant role in the intensity measurement. In addition, iron ions reduced the size of medium and small particles and their abundance. Furthermore, very large particles around 3 micrometers in size have diminished. If we recalculate the number of particles in the solutions, the size of the most abundant particles is 4 nm and this size is comparable to their mono- and bimetallic cousins. The particle size distribution of the mentioned NCs and TNCs according to intensities and number of particles are depicted in graphs; see SI Figures S2 and S3, respectively.

Table 6. Zeta potential values of BSA-Au, BSA-Au-Ag(a), BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a), BSA-Au-Ag(b), BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b) and appropriate standard deviations.

Sample	Zeta potential [mV]	Deviation [mV]
BSA-Nature	-23.0	1.7
BSA-Treated	-29.2	0.8
BSA-Au	-16.1	1.8
BSA-Fe(a)	-37.5	1.4
BSA-Fe(b)	-30.5	1.4
BSA-Au-Ag(a)	-13.5	1.2
BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)	-31.5	0.7
BSA-Au-Ag(b)	-19.0	1.0
BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)	-30.3	0.6

As it was demonstrated by several authors, the charge of the BSA-AuNCs envelope depends on the purity of BSA and/or the presence fatty acid in BSA [76]. The charge of the NCs envelope plays an important role in further utilization of NCs as a biological sensors/probes [49,85].

Results and deviations of the zeta potential measurements of our samples are listed in Table 6. The zeta potential of BSA dissolved in water and its dependence on pH condition was already reported by [77]. The charge of BSA at pH 7 reported by Li et al. was -20.3 ± 2.1 mV while we have measured -23 ± 1.7 mV [77]. The acidification, alkalisation, and heating processes change the charge of BSA-Nature to be more negative, as can be seen for BSA-Treated. However, the addition of gold ions to the BSA solution led to less negative change in the charge of the BSA-AuNCs at -16.1 ± 1.8 mV (Table 6). These results are in good correlation with the values revealed by Andryšková et al. where the average charge of BSA-AuNCs was determined to be -16 ± 0.7 mV [76]. Slightly more negatively charged BSA-AuNCs -19.2 mV incubated at pH 10 were reported by [74]. Only a few authors have reported on the charge of bimetallic BSA-AuAgNCs. One of them is Dutta et al. [49] according to their observation, the charge of unmodified BSA-Ag-AgNCs is approximately -12 mV, while we have measured -13.5 ± 1.2 mV and -19 ± 1 mV for BSA-Ag-Ag((a), (b))NCs, respectively [49]. The charge of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs is an uncharted area of research. However, Wang et al. [60] reported of BSA-Fe SPION which has a very strong negative charge of approximately around -38.5 mV and a very similar negative charge was measured for samples of BSA-Fe ((a), (b))NCs [60]. According to our results, BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs have a strong negative charge of approximately -31.5 ± 0.7 and -30.3 ± 0.6 mV, respectively. It can be speculated that the addition of Au ions at certain concentrations and conditions may lead to a reduction of the negative charge of the BSA-Treated; furthermore, a similar effect was observed for some concentrations of Ag ions. However, the addition of Fe ions had the opposite effect.

3.3. Protein conformation of BSA and BSA-NCs

The CD technique can be used to reveal the secondary protein structure of BSA-AuNCs, as demonstrated by these authors [76]. It is well known that the BSA structure changes during the heating process caused by MW irradiation or IR radiation, and some of the secondary structure changes are observed only when the temperature, pH, or other conditions reach a certain limit, and these changes are described in different ways [32,77, 84,86–88].

CD study was conducted as described in Andryšková et al. We have employed the BeStSel algorithm (graphs of structural changes measured by CD are shown in SI Figure S4) for the evaluation of CD spectra or calculated using Equations (2) and (3) inspired by [70,76]. The results are given in Table 7.

The CD confirmed the decrease of the alpha helix and the simultaneous increase of the other structures, turn or parallel/antiparallel in the process of denaturalization of BSA (BSA-Treated); similar results were observed by [76,77]. For BSA-Fe((a), (b))NCs a large increase in the representation of the alpha helix in the extent of other structures was observed as a function of the increasing concentration of the Fe ions, indicating that Fe ions are indeed capped by BSA. The addition of Ag ions in the ratio (0:1:0) has increased the representation of the alpha-helix in the secondary structure of the BSA, nevertheless the Ag ratio (0:2:0) has little effect compared to its denatured state BSA-Treated. However, Au ions embedded in BSA slightly reduced the amount of alpha helix compared to BSA-Ag(b)NCs, comparative study was performed by [32,55]. Yue et al. [55] also reported on combination of Au and Ag ions

Table 7. Calculated alpha-helix content in albumin either by using BeStSel algorithm, or MRE values. The changes of alpha-helix, Beta-sheet antiparallel + parallel and turn + other structure dependent on the type of sample are listed.

Sample	BeStSel suma alpha-helix [%]	BeStSel beta-sheet antiparalle + paralel [%]	BeStSel turn + others [%]	Equations (2) and (3) alpha-helix [%]
BSA-Nature	53.4	4.2	42.3	71.1
BSA-Treated	39.1	6.7	54.3	57.9
BSA-Ag(a)	44.8	5.3	49.8	66.3
BSA-Ag(b)	39.8	5.5	54.7	58.7
BSA-Au	32.5	10.9	56.7	51.5
BSA-Fe(a)	44.5	4.6	50.9	64.7
BSA-Fe(b)	55.9	7.1	37.0	77.8
BSA-Au-Ag(a)	33.3	9	57.8	51.4
BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)	35	10.1	54.9	51.1
BSA-Au-Ag(b)	47.3	8.2	44.5	57.3
BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)	26.1	19.5	54.4	41.0

incorporated into BSA that lead to further but not dramatic changes in the secondary structure of BSA [55]. While combinations of both Au and Ag ions in formed BSA-Au-Ag(a)NCs have caused only a slight increase in the representation of the alpha helix, a more pronounced increase of the alpha helix and a decrease of other secondary structures were observed in the BSA-Au-Ag(b)NCs, compared to BSA-AuNCs. The introduction of Fe ions has an opposite effect for each ratio of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs, while in the case of BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a)TNCs it led to an increase in the ordered structure, in BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(b)TNCs, Fe ions caused a large decrease in the ordered structure in the protein compared to their bimetallic cousins BSA-Au-Ag((a), (b))NCs, respectively. Well, our observations obtained by the BeStSel algorithm indicated that probably all metal ions have their own impact on the secondary structure of BSA, depending on the concentration of ions embedded in BSA, on the presence of other ions, and even on their mutual molar rations.

According to the literature, BSA-Nature should consist of 67% alpha-helix, 10% turn, 23% random coil, and no beta-sheet [86]. In compare our BSA-Treated which has been exposed to chemical, pH condition from acidic to alkaline and temperature stress up to 55 °C with the findings of [88] who only exposed the BSA to elevated temperature and to MW radiation, the obtained results are in good agreement, see Table 7. Comparing the secondary structure of BSA-AuNCs with that reported by [55,87], a good agreement was found for the amount of alpha-helix and random coil structures, but a significant difference was observed in the amount of turn structure. This is probably caused by the different temperature conditions during the syntheses. These findings are with in agreement with [55].

As mentioned above, the introduction of each metal may change the inner and external interactions between the protein residues, leading to a conformational change in the secondary structure of BSA. These changes can be further observed as different particle size distributions by DLS technique caused by various hydrodynamic diameters, see Table 5. In addition, the measurement of the zeta potential indicates a strong dependence on the type, amount, and ration of the individual metal ions incorporated in BSA. Samples containing Fe possess a large negative charge which makes their size more stable during the dilution process; see Table 5. In conclusion from Tables 1, 6, and 7, it is clearly seen that for all the ions used (Au, Ag, Fe) in the rations employed, binding to BSA does indeed occur and it is manifested by changes in the secondary structure of the protein, charge, and size of the BSA-NCs.

3.4. Magnetic resonance images and relaxivities

Many authors use BSA as a shell for SPIONs and/or other additives for better *in vivo* biocompatibility and cell targeting, but without fluorescence effect[59–61,89,90]. In our study, we tried to form small MRI-active TNCs formed using Fe(II) chloride and BSA inspired by [19,63]. We investigated whether our systems could be utilized as an MRI probe, therefore we performed MR imaging to check sensitivity of MR method and MR relaxometry to assess MR relaxivities. To see the ability to enhance MRI contrast, the concertation gradient of 1x, 2x, 4x, 5x, pre-concentrated samples with the respect to the content of Fe ions incorporated in BSA were measured. The reason why most of the samples were filtrated, except for the highest 5x pre-concentrated samples was to ensure appropriate size of the particles and to demonstrate that even smaller sized particles may contribute to MRI contrast. As it was reported [91,92]

Figure 8. T1 and T2 weighted magnetic resonance (MR) images at 1.5T external magnetic field. Samples row (a) Au-Ag-Fe-BSA(a) depending on the content of Fe 0.2, 0.5, 1.1, 1.9 mM, respectively and row (b) Au-Ag-Fe-BSA(b) depending on the content of Fe 0.6, 0.5, 2.1, 4 mM, respectively. SNR means signal to noise ratio, CNR represents contrast to noise ratio, FSL is fractional signal loss in percentage.

most suitable size of particles for cellular uptake is about 50 nm in diameter and nanoparticles with 20 nm or less show greatest tumor penetration and the particles in diameter greater than 200 nm will be probably mostly accumulating in the liver and spleen [91,92]. Furthermore, it was reported that iron oxide nanoparticles particles coated of polyvinyl propylene of size about 100 nm exhibited the highest contrast enhancement compared to smaller particles [93]. As it can be seen in Table 5, our synthesis and filtration created particles with largest size around 200 nm or lesser for both BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs samples, thus making them suitable candidates for MRI. As it was expected, the relaxivities r_1 and r_2 depended on the different concentrations of Fe ions and probably on the mutual ratios of Au, Ag and Fe, the results are summarized in Table 1.

As demonstrated in Figure 8, the T₂-weighted MR images of water phantoms containing the BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs showed that concentration series of these samples affected the T₂ contrast; the MR signal changed from the lowest to the highest intensity depending on the iron concentration (Figure 4). This signal change was confirmed by the image parameters CNR and FSL, which characterise the contrast in the MR images and its change. Both CNR (>22) and FSL (>22) reach higher values for higher iron concentrations in T₂-weighted MR images for both types of nanoclusters. On the contrary, no effect was observed in the T₁-weighted MR images, quantitatively confirmed by low CNR values. The results of imaging data analysis were in accordance with the relaxometry results, where the high r_2/r_1 ratio (≥ 8) of both ((a), (b)) probes with different iron concentrations suggested their assignment as a 'negative' contrast agents [60,61, 64,94]. When we compare/elaborate these findings illustrated in Figure 8 and Table 1 the MR contrast depends on the concentration of Fe ions bounded to BSA, furthermore it seems that Fe which is bounded to BSA is superparamagnetic. Concentration series of relaxivity r_2 of the sample BSA-Au-Ag-Fe(a) is linear. Moreover, it can be said that the MR contrast also depends on the conformation of the iron NCs in BSA or perhaps on the structure of BSA itself [95].

3.5. Cell viability

As the biocompatibility is a crucial issue for possible future applications of our samples as a biocompatible probe for the visualisation (MRI, fluorescence imaging) and/or therapy of the carcinoma cells, when the therapy effect is triggered by an external factor similarly to PTT, PDT or radiotherapy [23,25, 82,96,97]. Cytotoxicity tests were performed for trimetallic BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs as illustrated in Figure 9. The HepG2 carcinoma cell line was chosen for experiment and these cells were treated for 24 h in three pre-concentrated variants labelled accordingly with approximate Au ions concentrations of 8.5, 5.5, 2.5 mM, respectively. Viability decreased substantially to only 40%, in the ratio containing an

Figure 9. Effect on viability of cells exposed to BSA-Au-Ag-Fe((a), (b))TNCs. Control without adding of BSA-treated was set as 100%. Treated cells were labelled for 24 h with solution containing proximately 8.5 (a), 5.5 (b), 2.5 (c) mM of Au ions. Data are expressed as a mean of three independent experiments \pm standard error of the mean.

approximate concentration of Au ions of 8.5 mM, which is highly toxic to cells. However, cell viability was substantially higher (80% and 85%, respectively) considering cells treated with lower concentrations of 5.5, 2.5 mM of Au ions in BSA-Au-Ag-FeTNCs. When compared to viability tests where BSA-Treated (1.35 mM) was added to cultivation media and used as a control, we can see slightly higher viability results for all treatments, see SI Figure S5. However, the viability is still only below 50% for the highest concentration of Au ions other treatments have viability 90% and higher. Based on the ISO10993 guideline, 80% is a threshold to define significant cytotoxicity. To the best of our knowledge, there are focused no publications on the viability testing of trimetallic particles containing Au-Ag-Fe ions. Therefore, we can compare our cytotoxicity results with bimetallic systems consisting of Au-Ag particles only. According to Turan et al. [98] who tested bimetallic particles Au-AgNCs, the presence of Ag in these nanoparticles with polymer of 3,4-dihydroxyphenyl-L-alanine protective coating resulted in a decrease in the viability of treated cells [98]. As shown by [99], where Au-Ag mats with different surface coatings were used, the level of cell toxicity was relevant to the release Ag into medium. This also corresponds with the results of [100], showing low cytotoxicity of samples labelled as Au-Ag@BSA nanoparticles, which explains why the bond between Au and Ag nanoparticles increases the oxidising power of silver and prevents its release into the medium. Thus, we assume that the high toxicity caused by the highest concentration of BSA-Au-Ag-FeTNCs in our case could be caused by a high content of Ag, which probably interacts with BSA in a mode which differs from the mode reported in ref. [100], while no toxicity of BSA-AuNCs was found in study [76], however, the concentration of Au ions is up to 30 times higher compared to Andrýsková et al. Furthermore, the Fe abundance in our preconcentrated samples exceeds 17 times the upper limit of Fe abundance in living organisms. Thus, possibly all the ions may be cytotoxic to cells, depending on their concentration and protein structure. The most toxic species would probably be Ag and Au ions in BSA-Au-Ag-FeTNCs. Furthermore, the concentration of BSA-Treated (1.35 mM) has slightly decrease viability of our cells and it seems that this concentration of BSA in cultivation media is somewhat inconvenient for the cells. It can be concluded the treatment process with the highest concentration of Au ions is toxic for the cells and all metal ions may play its part in it including even the relatively high concentration of BSA. Therefore, concentration limits of toxicity of our samples were revealed and further we will focus on the elucidation of interaction of TNCs with cells and on the improvement of their biocompatibility.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study refers about a successful and reproducible synthesis of Au-Ag-FeTNCs using BSA as the capping agent. It can be said that each metal ion incorporated into BSA has altered the structure of the protein, thus leading to the formation of TNCs with unique properties, as demonstrated by spectroscopic and other experimental techniques. Furthermore, most of the metal ions remained bound to the protein backbone despite dialysis, preconcentration, and filtration procedures, indicating well-stabilised nanoclusters. In general, the Ag ions have not only led to an alternation of the fluorescence properties compared to BSA-AuNCs as was demonstrated by the fluorescence intensity peak position shift and QY, but

also caused the formation of an altered size, charge, and shape of BSA-Au-AgNCs. Iron ions have been employed due to their potential as an MRI contrast agent. However, the synthesised TNCs proved to be suitable for use as MRI probes. In addition, the incorporation of Fe ions led to Coulombic stabilisation of the protein. Last, but not least, the limits of concentration were obtained that are still well tolerated by the Hep G2 cell line. This allows us to further investigate our samples as a potential bimodal probe and to expand the potential applications of our samples in nanomedicine. It should be stressed that, further investigation about the interaction of the metal ions and BSA must be carried out to eventually determine the preferential binding sites for each metal to further improve its properties and to choose a suitable targeting agent to expand the potential applications in nanomedicine.

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Authors' contributions

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Disclosure statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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